

Transformative landscape change to tackle the climate and biodiversity crises: a Scotland-wide zonation for restoration

Appendices

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Appendix 1. Methodological approaches

Appendix 1-a. Opportunity mapping – spatial multicriteria analysis

To highlight areas suitable for a type of change (e.g. woodland expansion), for each habitat expansion separately, a spatial multicriteria approach was followed combining multiple spatial layers. These include:

- i) target layers (binary, 1 = target), which define the initial overall spatial domain for a land conversion relevant to the focal habitat (e.g. “all intensive grasslands”).
- ii) positive layers (continuous values, 0 to 1), which indicate where -in the spatial domain - change from present land use to the focal habitat would be beneficial according to a certain criterion.
- iii) negative layers (continuous values, -1 to 0), which indicate where change would be possible, but detrimental according to a certain criterion and
- iv) excluded layers (binary, 0: excluded), which indicate areas where a certain type of change should not be permitted (e.g. planting trees on peatlands).

Details on the criteria for each habitat are provided in the methodological appendices (see their respective sections).

To highlight opportunity areas for each type of landscape change, all the relevant criteria layers were combined into a “Final Landscape Zonation map”, using the equation below. Notice that, as the multiplications ensure that the intersection defines the target areas.

Final continuous Landscape Zonation equation per habitat at each 100m cell:

(Equation 1)

$$\left(\prod \text{Target layers (default)} \text{ or } \sum \text{Target layers (if "Ta" instead of "T")} \right. \\ \times \left[\begin{array}{l} \left(\sum \text{all Positive layers} \right)_{\text{rescaled}} \\ + \left(\sum \text{all Negative layers} \right)_{\text{rescaled}} \end{array} \right]_{\text{rescaled}} \\ \times \prod \text{Exclusion layers} \\ \left. \right)_{\text{rescaled}}$$

with \sum : sum all; \prod : multiply all; rescaled: rescaled 0 to 1 across Scotland extent; Ta: additive Target layer; T: multiplicative Target layer.

In the tables of the methods (Appendix 2 to Appendix 8) we refer to the terms in Equation 1 with their initials (T,P,N,E). Notice that in not all layer types were used for every habitat.

Each resultant opportunity map was rescaled 0-1 and subdivided into 3 priority categories by using the 33rd and 66th quantiles as thresholds (later labelled as “Final 3 tiers Landscape Zonation” maps).

To highlight areas suitable for multiple types of change/restoration, the top priority areas for each habitat change type were then combined together (later labelled as “Final Landscape Zonation of High priorities” map).

Appendix 1-b. Summary statistics at catchments and sub-catchment levels

We also calculated statistics at the catchment and sub-catchment level. These two level of aggregation are justified by the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (MAUP), which consists of statistical bias in spatial analysis caused by arbitrary changes in spatial unit boundaries. The MAUP has two key effects: a scale effect, with results varying depending on the level of aggregation, and a zoning effect, with different ways of dividing the same area into zones can lead to different analytical outcomes. Calculating statistics at two levels of aggregation partly alleviates the problem, but referring to the raster maps is ultimately a way to clarifying patterns.

The first level of aggregation was the Scottish River catchments, the second the sub-catchments used by SEPA for water quality monitoring.

Using the raster map as components, we created 3 thematic groups: i) agroecology (agroforestry, AEM), ii) woodlands (woodlands, riparian woodlands and deer pressure), and iii) high nature value grasslands and heathland maps. Only cells belonging to the highest priority class in any of the components were included, to form a thematic binary raster, which was used to calculate catchment statistics.

For both levels of aggregation, we calculated P as the number of 100 m high priority cells and normalised by catchment area to avoid area bias. We then ranked the catchments based on this statistic.

For the Scottish catchments we present the priority classes based on the cumulative value of P. We split the range of P in 10 intervals or classes of priority and find the catchments that correspond to that class.

Appendix 1-1. Agroecology groups (1= highest priority)

Technically, an exponential function of the form:

$$(Equation 2) \quad y = C * (1 - \exp(-x / \alpha))$$

was used, where:

- C represents the plateau value.
- alpha is the parameter that controls the rate of growth.
- x is the independent variable, here cumulative area.

Using observed data points, a nonlinear least squares regression was performed to estimate and C and alpha. The model was fitted in R using the nls() function.

To divide the curve into ten intervals, we determined the values of x corresponding to 10% to 90% of the plateau, using:

$$(Equation\ 3) \quad x_p = -\alpha * \log(pc)$$

where pc is the corresponding complement of the percentage interval (e.g., pc = 0.1 for 90%, pc = 0.2 for 80%, etc.)

Appendix 1-2. Cumulative area vs cumulative priority index P and intervals on the curve.

The catchments were sorted by P and then 10 classes were defined based on how the intervals of P divided the cumulative area range.

Rationale and data sources for each landscape -level change proposed

The opportunity maps presented in this work are based on tens of component layers, each often the product of a detailed analysis, such as mechanistic or statistical modelling, or spatial analysis.

Appendix 2. Woodlands

The expansion of woodlands is a fundamental component in the broader strategy of nature conservation and climate change mitigation, in many countries, including Scotland. Strategic spatial planning, informed by ecological principles, can ensure that woodland expansion contributes positively to our environment and to the well-being of both rural and urban communities.

By strategically mapping out areas for woodland expansion, we can target areas where it would be more important to harness the natural benefits that these ecosystems provide, such as, the mitigation of diffuse pollution and of flood risk, and the storage of carbon. Moreover, the establishment of new native woodlands is important to promote biodiversity by providing habitat and stepping stones that enhance connectivity.

A diverse woodland is more resilient to the impacts of climate change and is better equipped to provide habitat for a wide range of species. By increasing the connectivity between existing woodland areas, we can facilitate the movement of species that have relatively short dispersal distances across the landscape, which is essential for maintaining genetic diversity, supporting wildlife corridors, and enabling species to adapt to changing conditions.

The planning for woodland expansion must be ecologically sensitive, avoiding, for example, areas of high conservation value such as species-rich grasslands, wader's habitat, and vital carbon sinks like peatlands and other organic soils. Instead, focus should be placed on areas that would benefit most from afforestation, based on a number of benefits.

Encouraging the natural or assisted regeneration of native species ensures that woodlands develop in a way that supports local ecosystems and provides habitat for wildlife. However, due to dispersal constraints, this is usually appropriate only within a limited distance from existing native woodlands.

Commercial plantations can provide some of the above benefits with emphasis on timber and carbon storage but have also potential trade-offs with biodiversity and water quality, so they need to be carefully planned and preferably managed for multi-functional uses.

Appendix 2-1 and Appendix 2-2 below summarises spatial criteria maps that were used to assess suitability for expansion.

Appendix 2-1. Layers included in the Woodland zonation maps. The “Type” column refers to Equation 1 with T: target areas, P: positive criteria, N: negative criteria, E: exclusion areas. Cf. Appendix 2-2 for individual maps.

Type	Topic	Name	References
T	Grasslands	All grasslands + heathers	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O’Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc
P	Connectivity corridors	Broadleaves connectivity corridors	Castellazzi M., Gimona A. (2018). Lemmings tool: assessing functional connectivity based on random walk of individuals in a vector landscape under land use and climate change - Part of RESAS 1.4.2cii [Deliverable 10] - Beta version of vector-based connectivity tool. Castellazzi, M.; Baggio, A.; Gimona, A., (2021) Climate-friendly (inspired by NetZero) land use scenario for multi-benefits: assessing broadleaves connectivity with the Lemmings tool., Part of RESAS O1.4.2ciiD29: Connectivity Analysis for Forests and Heather Habitats. (PowerPoint Summary). Gimona, A., Poggio, L., Brown, I., Castellazzi, M. (2012) Woodland networks in a changing climate: Threats from land use change. Biological Conservation. Vol 149, issue 1, p.93-102. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.01.060 Morton D., Rowland C., Wood C., Meek L., Marston c., Smith G., Wadsworth R., Simpson I.C. (2011) Final Report for LCM2007 - the new UK Land Cover Map. CEH. https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/LCM2007%20Final%20Report.pdf Patterson G., Nelson, D., Robertson P., Tullis J. (2014) Scotland’s Native Woodlands Results from the Native Woodland Survey of Scotland. Forestry Commission Scotland, Edinburgh, UK. Forestry Commission (2015) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2015. https://www.forestryresearch.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/national-forest-inventory/ [accessed 05/07/22]
P	Connectivity corridors	ScotPine connectivity corridors	Castellazzi M., Gimona A. (2018). Lemmings tool: assessing functional connectivity based on random walk of individuals in a vector landscape under land use and climate change - Part of RESAS 1.4.2cii [Deliverable 10] - Beta version of vector-based connectivity tool. Castellazzi, M.; Baggio, A.; Gimona, A., (2021) Climate-friendly (inspired by NetZero) land use scenario for multi-benefits: assessing broadleaves connectivity with the Lemmings tool., Part of RESAS O1.4.2ciiD29: Connectivity Analysis for Forests and Heather Habitats. (PowerPoint Summary). Scottish Forestry Open Data (2018) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). Caledonian Pinewood Inventory - data.gov.uk [accessed 05/07/22] NatureScot (2019) National Vegetation Classification (NVC) survey. SpatialData.gov.scot [accessed 05/07/22] Patterson G., Nelson, D., Robertson P., Tullis J. (2014) Scotland’s Native Woodlands Results from the Native Woodland Survey of Scotland. Forestry Commission Scotland, Edinburgh, UK. https://forestry.gov.scot/publications/74-scotland-s-native-woodlands-results-from-the-native-woodland-survey-of-scotland/download [accessed 05/07/22] Forestry Commission (2015) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2015. National Forest Inventory - Forest Research [accessed 05/07/22] Morton D., Rowland C., Wood C., Meek L., Marston c., Smith G., Wadsworth R., Simpson I.C. (2011) Final Report for LCM2007 - the new UK Land Cover Map. CEH. https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/LCM2007%20Final%20Report.pdf
P	Conservation	Natural regeneration (1km from native woodlands)	Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). https://open-data-Caledonian-Pinewood-Inventory-data.gov.uk Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2020, https://data-forestry.opendata.arcgis.com/datasets/0681a879417b42dfb6d7825ef791cd5a_0/explorer?location=56.121863%2C-4.501302%2C6.98
P	Fluvial risk	Fluvial risk (high; from EcoForest tool)	Gimona, A., Castellazzi, M., Wilkins B., Baggio-Compagnucci, A. (2022) ECOFOREST: Spatial multi-criteria analysis to prioritise planting at the landscape level, Metadata and Further information - Fluvial Risk. Online. https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/212a7f8600314ad38d074769c3500f61#ref-n-9zP92k [accessed 07/01/25]
P	Grazing	All land grazed above conservation threshold	Baseline dataset from : Castellazzi, M., Gimona, A., Wardell-Johnson, D., Miller, D., Rivington, M., & Matthews, K. (2024). A SSP1-Low emission land use scenario based on LCM2019 for Scotland - baseline 2019 and scenario 2050 (nov22) [Data set]. https://openscience.hutton.ac.uk/dataset/low-emission-land-use-scenarios , Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10927157 Based on the following : Wardell-Johnson, D. (2022) IACS 2019 v4. Based on data from Land Parcel Information System (2019) courtesy of Rural Payments and Inspections Division, Scottish Government. Based on data from the June Agricultural Census (2019) courtesy of Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services, Agricultural Statistics team, Scottish Government. Morton, R.D., Marston, C.G., O’Neil, A.W., Rowland, C.S., (2020) Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc SSP1-Low emission story map: https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/c3d3feff85f14460b6c973127089d6f9
P	Pollination	Pollination for food production (low)	Gimona, A., Baggio-Compagnucci, A., Poggio, L., Brooker R., Pakeman, R., Simonetti E., Castellazzi, M. (2018) Indicators of Ecosystem Services in Scotland, including Pollination Index. https://arcg.is/0v04WH [accessed 05/07/22]
P	Rivers	Nutrient export (high)	Sharp, R., Tallis, H.T., Ricketts, T., Guerry, A.D., Wood, S.A., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Nelson, E., Ennaanay, D., Wolny, S., Olwero, N. and Vigerstol, K., (2014). InVEST 3.0.0 User’s Guide. The Natural Capital Project: Stanford University, University of Minnesota, The Nature Conservancy, and World Wildlife Fund. https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest
P	Rivers	Risk of Phosphorus leaching (high)	For non-agricultural land : implementation of rules of the PLUS+ model for slope and land cover. Donnelly, D., Booth, P., Ferrier, R., Futter, M. (2011) Phosphorus Land Use and Slope (PLUS+) Model, User Guide & Computer code (version 1.6). https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/Plus+%20User%20Guide%20-%20v1_6.pdf [accessed 09/01/25] For agricultural land : Gagkas, Z., Lilly, A., Baggaley, N., Stutter, M. (2019) Development of framework for a Red-Amber-Green assessment on phosphorus application to land. Technical report. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34519.19365
P	Rivers	Sediment export (high)	Sharp, R., Tallis, H.T., Ricketts, T., Guerry, A.D., Wood, S.A., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Nelson, E., Ennaanay, D., Wolny, S., Olwero, N. and Vigerstol, K., (2014). InVEST 3.0.0 User’s Guide. The Natural Capital Project: Stanford University, University of Minnesota, The Nature Conservancy, and World Wildlife Fund. https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest
P	Rivers	Water Overall Ecology 2023, Bad and Poor catchments	SEPA (2024) Water Classification Hub: Overall Ecology for 2023, surface water. https://informatics.sepa.org.uk/WaterClassificationHub/ [accessed 05/12/24] “Contains SEPA data © Scottish Environment Protection Agency and database right [2023]. All rights reserved”. Open Government Licence version 3.0 . Required Acknowledgements: © SEPA. Some features of this information are based on digital spatial data licensed from the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology © NERC (CEH). Contains OS data © Crown copyright [and database right].
P	Soil	Carbon Budget (Positive)	Baggio-Compagnucci A., Ovando P., Hewitt R.J., Canullo R., Gimona, A. (2022) Barking up the wrong tree? Can forest expansion help meet climate goals? Environmental Science & Policy. vol.136, p.237-249. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.05.011 .

N	Conservation	Waders outside Conservation areas	Newey, S., Fielding, D., Wilson, M. (2020) Mapping farmland wader distributions and population change to identify wader priority areas for conservation and management action. https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/Newey_et_al_IdentifyingWaderPriorityAreas_InternallyReviewed%26%20Signedoff_FINAL.pdf [accessed 05/07/22] Conservation areas: available from https://data.gov.uk/
N	Soil	Carbon Budget (Negative)	Baggio-Compagnucci A., Ovando P., Hewitt R.J., Canullo R., Gimona, A. (2022) Barking up the wrong tree? Can forest expansion help meet climate goals? Environmental Science & Policy. vol. 136, p. 237-249. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.05.011 .
E	Conservation	Arable conservation + 2km	Pakeman, R., McKeen, M. (2019). Within country targeting of agri-environment funding: A test of different methods. Global Ecology and Conservation. 17. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00574 Gimona, A., McKeen, M., Baggio, A., Simonetti, E., Poggio, L., Pakeman, R.J. (2023) Complementary effects of biodiversity and ecosystem services on spatial targeting for agri-environment payments. Land Use Policy 126, 106532. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106532
E	Conservation	Grass conservation + 2km	Pakeman, R., McKeen, M. (2019). Within country targeting of agri-environment funding: A test of different methods. Global Ecology and Conservation. 17. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00574 Gimona, A., McKeen, M., Baggio, A., Simonetti, E., Poggio, L., Pakeman, R.J. (2023) Complementary effects of biodiversity and ecosystem services on spatial targeting for agri-environment payments. Land Use Policy 126, 106532. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106532
E	Conservation	Moorland high connectivity	Castellazzi M., Gimona A. (2018). Lemmings tool: assessing functional connectivity based on random walk of individuals in a vector landscape under land use and climate change - Part of RESAS 1.4.2cii [Deliverable 10] - Beta version of vector-based connectivity tool. Castellazzi M., Hewitt R., Gimona A. (2021) SSP1 & SSP5 land use scenarios (50 replicates, November 2020) to estimate 3 Habitats connectivity (Broadleaves, Moorland, Scot Pine) with the Lemmings tool [part of RESAS O 1.4.2ciiD29: Connectivity analysis for forests and heather habitats]. Powerpoint Summary. Ersoy, E., Jorgensen, A, Warren, P.H. (2019) Identifying multispecies connectivity corridors and the spatial pattern of the landscape. Urban Forestry & Urban Greening. Vol 40, pp.308-322 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2018.08.001 . [adapted for land use classes and model characteristics] Morton D., Rowland C., Wood C., Meek L., Marston c., Smith G., Wadsworth R., Simpson I.C. (2011) Final Report for LCM2007 - the new UK Land Cover Map. CEH. https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/LCM2007%20Final%20Report.pdf Patterson G., Nelson, D., Robertson P., Tullis J. (2014) Scotland's Native Woodlands Results from the Native Woodland Survey of Scotland. Forestry Commission Scotland, Edinburgh, UK. Forestry Commission (2015) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2015. https://www.forestryresearch.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/national-forest-inventory/ [accessed 05/07/22] Scottish Government (2015) Integrated Administrative and Control System (IACS) for 2015. https://www.ruralpayments.org/topics/apply-for-funding/single-application-form/ [accessed 05/07/22]
E	Conservation	Top Waders outside conservation (0.5Mha) + 2km	Newey, S., Fielding, D., Wilson, M. (2020) Mapping farmland wader distributions and population change to identify wader priority areas for conservation and management action. https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/Newey_et_al_IdentifyingWaderPriorityAreas_InternallyReviewed%26%20Signedoff_FINAL.pdf [accessed 05/07/22] Conservation areas: available from https://data.gov.uk/
E	Conservation	Waders in riparian habitat within protected areas	Newey, S., Fielding, D., Wilson, M. (2020) Mapping farmland wader distributions and population change to identify wader priority areas for conservation and management action. https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/Newey_et_al_IdentifyingWaderPriorityAreas_InternallyReviewed%26%20Signedoff_FINAL.pdf [accessed 05/07/22] OS Mastermap® Networks Water Layer https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/mastermap-water [accessed 05/07/22] Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc Protected areas: available from https://data.gov.uk/
E	Physical restrictions	(sub-)Urban, rocks, sediments, water from LCM19	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc
E	Physical restrictions	Bog, Fen from LCM19	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc
E	Physical restrictions	DAMs score (High winds)	Forest Research (2015) Detailed Aspect Method of Scoring (DAMS). https://www.forestresearch.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/ftmr/forestgales/how-forestgales-works/ [accessed 05/07/22] Quine, C.P., White, I.M.S. (1993) Revised Windiness Scores for the Windthrow Hazard Classification: the Revised Scoring Method. Information Note No. 230. Forestry Commission, Edinburgh.
E	Physical restrictions	Inland Water	OS Mastermap® Topographic Layer https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/mastermap-topography [accessed 05/07/22]
E	Physical restrictions	Roads, Railways	OS Mastermap® Topographic Layer https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/mastermap-topography [accessed 05/07/22]
E	Policy	Gardens, designed landscapes	Historic Environment Scotland (2021) Gardens, designed landscapes. https://data.gov.uk/dataset/bab10bd8-cc8b-4b4e-9eb7-d620a3ee27d9/gardens-and-designed-landscapes [accessed 05/07/22]
E	Policy	SSSI & SAC (not wood, not Salmon)	Scottish Government (2021) Special Area of Conservation (Scotland). https://data.gov.uk/dataset/2559b8bc-ddd6-4cb1-8a98-9422e1b1865a/special-area-of-conservation-scotland [accessed 05/07/22] Scottish Government (2021) Site of Special Scientific Interest (Scotland). https://data.gov.uk/dataset/d64bf689-4ce8-465b-b00e-6a57dec94a22/site-of-special-scientific-interest-scotland [accessed 05/07/22]
E	Policy	Scheduled Monuments	Historic Environment Scotland (2021) Scheduled Monuments. https://data.gov.uk/dataset/9075113f-d8e3-48da-bbfc-34f58939529b/scheduled-monuments [accessed 05/07/22]
E	Soil	Deep Peat & carbon rich soils (SNH)	Scottish Natural Heritage (SNH) (2016) Carbon and Peatland 2016 map. https://spatialdata.gov.scot/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/51b36efb-3521-4243-9bb0-93f8a7a60a71 [accessed 05/07/22]

Appendix 2-2. All layers included in the Woodland zonation, cf. Appendix 2-1 for references. Colour coding is as follows, blue: target layers, purple: positive layers, orange: negative layers, black: exclusion layers.

Appendix 2-3. Main component and final landscape zonation (0 to 1) for Woodland (left). Calculation of the Final continuous map (right) = rescaled (Positive + Negative) x Exclusion x Target.

Appendix 2-4. Final 3 tiers zonation for woodlands, in the brackets: hectare and % of Scotland extent.

Appendix 3. Decreasing deer pressure to support woodland regeneration

Areas with high deer pressure (> 5 deer per km²) next to existing native woodlands were identified, and a 1-km buffer constructed. However, it should be noted that the deer density map is relatively old (2010) and reflects were deer that were spotted on open grounds; thus, the deer population close to woodlands might be underestimated.

Appendix 3-1. Layers included in the Decreasing Deer pressure zonation maps. The “Type” column refers to Equation 1 with T: target areas, P: positive criteria, N: negative criteria, E: exclusion areas. Cf. Appendix 3-2 for individual maps.

Type	Topic	Name	References
T	Grazing	Wild deer count (NatureScot, 2010) above 5 deer / km ²	NatureScot (2010) Deer Counts Deer groups. https://opendata.nature.scot/datasets/snh::deer-counts-deer-groups/about [accessed 11/12/24] © Scottish Natural Heritage; Available under the Open Government Licence http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/
P	Regeneration woodlands	1km buffer around Native Broadleaves (NWSS)	Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about
P	Regeneration woodlands	1km buffer around Native Coniferous (CPI, NWSS)	Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). https://open-data-Caledonian-Pinewood-Inventory-data.gov.uk Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about

Appendix 3-2. All layers included in the decreasing deer pressure to support woodland regeneration zonation, cf. Appendix 3-1 for references. Colour coding is as follows, blue: target layers, purple: positive layers, orange: negative layers, black: exclusion layers.

Appendix 3-3. Main component and final landscape zonation (0 to 1) for Woodland (left). Calculation of the Final continuous map (right) = rescaled (Positive + Negative) x Exclusion x Target.

Appendix 3-4. Final 3 tiers zonation for decreasing deer pressure to support woodland regeneration, in the brackets: hectare and % of Scotland extent.

Appendix 4. Agroforestry

Agroforestry has similar benefits to those discussed for woodlands and also offers unique advantages, particularly in agricultural landscapes, as it allows the blending of agricultural activities and tree growing at the landscape level. Agroforestry therefore addresses both the need for sustainable food production and the provision of environmental benefits.

Among the benefits, the integration of trees into farming systems enhances carbon sequestration, thus contributing to climate mitigation. In agricultural settings, agroforestry can also serve to create a more beneficial microclimate, providing shade and reducing the temperature extremes that can stress crops and livestock. This microclimatic regulation is increasingly important as global temperatures rise. Additionally, the root systems of trees enhance soil structure, reducing the risk of flood through improved water infiltration and decreasing the risk soil erosion, which is a significant concern in agricultural lands where soil is a critical resource.

Beyond the environmental benefits, agroforestry contributes to biodiversity in some species-poor agricultural landscapes. The presence of trees creates habitats for a variety of species, from invertebrates, which play essential roles in soil health and pollination, to birds, which contribute to pest control and seed dispersal. This increase in biodiversity not only supports ecosystem health but can also enhance agricultural productivity and resilience.

Recognizing these benefits, new funding mechanisms for land management could prioritize and incentivise the adoption of agroforestry practices. This approach aligns economic incentives with environmental stewardship.

Appendix 4-1. Layers included in the Agroforestry zonation maps. The “Type” column refers to Equation 1 with T: target areas, P: positive criteria, N: negative criteria, E: exclusion areas. Cf. Appendix 4-2 for individual maps.

Type	Topic	Name	References
T	Agriculture	Arable + Grasslands (improved & semi-natural; LCM19)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O’Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc
P	Connectivity corridors	Broadleaves connectivity corridors	Castellazzi M., Gimona A. (2018). Lemmings tool: assessing functional connectivity based on random walk of individuals in a vector landscape under land use and climate change - Part of RESAS 1.4.2cii [Deliverable 10] - Beta version of vector-based connectivity tool. Castellazzi, M.; Baggio, A.; Gimona, A., (2021) Climate-friendly (inspired by NetZero) land use scenario for multi-benefits: assessing broadleaves connectivity with the Lemmings tool., Part of RESAS O1.4.2ciiD29: Connectivity Analysis for Forests and Heather Habitats. (PowerPoint Summary). Gimona, A., Poggio, L., Brown, I., Castellazzi, M. (2012) Woodland networks in a changing climate: Threats from land use change. Biological Conservation. Vol 149, issue 1, p.93-102. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.01.060 Morton D., Rowland C., Wood C., Meek L., Marston c., Smith G., Wadsworth R., Simpson I.C. (2011) Final Report for LCM2007 - the new UK Land Cover Map. CEH. https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/LCM2007%20Final%20Report.pdf Patterson G., Nelson, D., Robertson P., Tullis J. (2014) Scotland’s Native Woodlands Results from the Native Woodland Survey of Scotland. Forestry Commission Scotland, Edinburgh, UK. https://www.forestry.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/national-forest-inventory/ [accessed 05/07/22]
P	Connectivity corridors	ScotPines connectivity corridors	Castellazzi M., Gimona A. (2018). Lemmings tool: assessing functional connectivity based on random walk of individuals in a vector landscape under land use and climate change - Part of RESAS 1.4.2cii [Deliverable 10] - Beta version of vector-based connectivity tool. Castellazzi, M.; Baggio, A.; Gimona, A., (2021) Climate-friendly (inspired by NetZero) land use scenario for multi-benefits: assessing broadleaves connectivity with the Lemmings tool., Part of RESAS O1.4.2ciiD29: Connectivity Analysis for Forests and Heather Habitats. (PowerPoint Summary). Scottish Forestry Open Data (2018) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). Caledonian Pinewood Inventory - data.gov.uk [accessed 05/07/22] NatureScot (2019) National Vegetation Classification (NVC) survey. SpatialData.gov.scot [accessed 05/07/22] Patterson G., Nelson, D., Robertson P., Tullis J. (2014) Scotland’s Native Woodlands Results from the Native Woodland Survey of Scotland. Forestry Commission Scotland, Edinburgh, UK. https://forestry.gov.scot/publications/74-scotland-s-native-woodlands-results-from-the-native-woodland-survey-of-scotland/download [accessed 05/07/22]

			Forestry Commission (2015) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2015. National Forest Inventory - Forest Research [accessed 05/07/22] https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/LCM2007%20Final%20Report.pdf
P	Fluvial risk	Fluvial risk (high; from EcoForest tool)	Gimona, A., Castellazzi, M., Wilkins B., Baggio-Compagnucci, A. (2022) ECOFOREST: Spatial multi-criteria analysis to prioritise planting at the landscape level, Metadata and Further information - Fluvial Risk. Online. https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/212a7f8600314ad38d074769c3500f61#ref-n-9zP92k [accessed 07/01/25]
P	Grazing	All Grasslands (A, IG, SNG) - grazed above conservation threshold	Baseline dataset from : Castellazzi, M., Gimona, A., Wardell-Johnson, D., Miller, D., Rivington, M., & Matthews, K. (2024). A SSP1-Low emission land use scenario based on LCM2019 for Scotland - baseline 2019 and scenario 2050 (nov22) [Data set]. https://opencscience.hutton.ac.uk/dataset/low-emission-land-use-scenarios , Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10927157 Based on the following : Wardell-Johnson, D. (2022) IACS 2019 v4. Based on data from Land Parcel Information System (2019) courtesy of Rural Payments and Inspections Division, Scottish Government. Based on data from the June Agricultural Census (2019) courtesy of Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services, Agricultural Statistics team, Scottish Government. Morton, R.D., Marston, C.G., O'Neil, A.W., Rowland, C.S., (2020) Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc SSP1-Low emission story map: https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/c3d3feff85f14460b6c973127089d6f9
P	Pollination	Pollination for food production (low)	Gimona, A., Baggio-Compagnucci, A., Poggio, L., Brooker R., Pakeman, R., Simonetti E., Castellazzi, M. (2018) Indicators of Ecosystem Services in Scotland, including Pollination Index. https://arcg.is/0v04WH [accessed 05/07/22]
P	Rivers	Nutrient export (high)	Sharp, R., Tallis, H.T., Ricketts, T., Guerry, A.D., Wood, S.A., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Nelson, E., Ennaanay, D., Wolny, S., Olwero, N. and Vigerstol, K., (2014). InVEST 3.0.0 User's Guide. The Natural Capital Project: Stanford University, University of Minnesota, The Nature Conservancy, and World Wildlife Fund. https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest
P	Rivers	Risk of Phosphorus leaching (high)	For non-agricultural land : implementation of rules of the PLUS+ model for slope and land cover. Donnelly, D., Booth, P., Ferrier, R., Futter, M. (2011) Phosphorus Land Use and Slope (PLUS+) Model, User Guide & Computer code (version 1.6). https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/Plus+%20User%20Guide%20-%20v1.6.pdf [accessed 09/01/25] For agricultural land : Gagkas, Z., Lilly, A., Baggaley, N., Stutter, M. (2019) Development of framework for a Red-Amber-Green assessment on phosphorus application to land. Technical report. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34519.19365
P	Rivers	Sediment export (high)	Sharp, R., Tallis, H.T., Ricketts, T., Guerry, A.D., Wood, S.A., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Nelson, E., Ennaanay, D., Wolny, S., Olwero, N. and Vigerstol, K., (2014). InVEST 3.0.0 User's Guide. The Natural Capital Project: Stanford University, University of Minnesota, The Nature Conservancy, and World Wildlife Fund. https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest
P	Rivers	Water Overall Ecology 2023, Bad and Poor catchments	SEPA (2024) Water Classification Hub: Overall Ecology for 2023, surface water. https://informatics.sepa.org.uk/WaterClassificationHub/ [accessed 05/12/24] "Contains SEPA data © Scottish Environment Protection Agency and database right [2023]. All rights reserved" Open Government Licence version 3.0. Required Acknowledgements: © SEPA. Some features of this information are based on digital spatial data licensed from the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology © NERC (CEH). Contains OS data © Crown copyright [and database right].
N	Conservation	Waders outside Conservation areas	Newey, S., Fielding, D., Wilson, M. (2020) Mapping farmland wader distributions and population change to identify wader priority areas for conservation and management action. https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/Newey_et_al_IdentifyingWaderPriorityAreas_InternallyReviewed%26%20Signedoff_FINAL.pdf [accessed 05/07/22] Conservation areas: available from https://data.gov.uk/
N	Soil	Carbon Budget (Negative)	Baggio-Compagnucci A., Ovando P., Hewitt R.J., Canullo R., Gimona, A. (2022) Barking up the wrong tree? Can forest expansion help meet climate goals? Environmental Science & Policy. vol.136, p.237-249. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.05.011 .
E	Conservation	Arable conservation + 2km	Pakeman, R., McKeen, M. (2019). Within country targeting of agri-environment funding: A test of different methods. Global Ecology and Conservation. 17. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00574 Gimona, A., McKeen, M., Baggio, A., Simonetti, E., Poggio, L., Pakeman, R.J. (2023) Complementary effects of biodiversity and ecosystem services on spatial targeting for agri-environment payments. Land Use Policy 126, 106532. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106532
E	Conservation	Grass conservation + 2km	Pakeman, R., McKeen, M. (2019). Within country targeting of agri-environment funding: A test of different methods. Global Ecology and Conservation. 17. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00574 Gimona, A., McKeen, M., Baggio, A., Simonetti, E., Poggio, L., Pakeman, R.J. (2023) Complementary effects of biodiversity and ecosystem services on spatial targeting for agri-environment payments. Land Use Policy 126, 106532. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106532
E	Conservation	Moorland high connectivity	Castellazzi M., Gimona A. (2018). Lemmings tool: assessing functional connectivity based on random walk of individuals in a vector landscape under land use and climate change - Part of RESAS 1.4.2cii [Deliverable 10] - Beta version of vector-based connectivity tool. Castellazzi M., Hewitt R., Gimona A. (2021) SSP1 & SSP5 land use scenarios (50 replicates, November 2020) to estimate 3 Habitats connectivity (Broadleaves, Moorland, Scot Pine) with the Lemmings tool [part of RESAS O1.4.2ciiD29: Connectivity analysis for forests and heather habitats]. Powerpoint Summary. Ersoy, E., Jorgensen, A, Warren, P.H. (2019) Identifying multispecies connectivity corridors and the spatial pattern of the landscape. Urban Forestry & Urban Greening. Vol 40, pp.308-322 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2018.08.001 . [adapted for land use classes and model characteristics]
			Morton D., Rowland C., Wood C., Meek L., Marston c., Smith G., Wadsworth R., Simpson I.C. (2011) Final Report for LCM2007 - the new UK Land Cover Map. CEH. https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/LCM2007%20Final%20Report.pdf Patterson G., Nelson, D., Robertson P., Tullis J. (2014) Scotland's Native Woodlands Results from the Native Woodland Survey of Scotland. Forestry Commission Scotland, Edinburgh, UK. Forestry Commission (2015) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2015. https://www.forestryresearch.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/national-forest-inventory/ [accessed 05/07/22] Scottish Government (2015) Integrated Administrative and Control System (IACS) for 2015. https://www.ruralpayments.org/topics/apply-for-funding/single-application-form/ [accessed 05/07/22]
E	Conservation	Top Waders outside conservation (0.5Mha) + 2km	Newey, S., Fielding, D., Wilson, M. (2020) Mapping farmland wader distributions and population change to identify wader priority areas for conservation and management action. https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/Newey_et_al_IdentifyingWaderPriorityAreas_InternallyReviewed%26%20Signedoff_FINAL.pdf [accessed 05/07/22] Conservation areas: available from https://data.gov.uk/
E	Conservation	Waders in riparian habitat within protected areas	Newey, S., Fielding, D., Wilson, M. (2020) Mapping farmland wader distributions and population change to identify wader priority areas for conservation and management action. https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/Newey_et_al_IdentifyingWaderPriorityAreas_InternallyReviewed%26%20Signedoff_FINAL.pdf [accessed 05/07/22] OS Mastermap® Networks Water Layer https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/mastermap-water [accessed 05/07/22] Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc Protected areas: available from https://data.gov.uk/
E	Physical restrictions	(sub-)Urban, rocks, sediments, water from LCM19	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc
E	Physical restrictions	Bog, Fen from LCM19	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc

E	Physical restrictions	DAMs score (High winds)	Forest Research (2015) Detailed Aspect Method of Scoring (DAMS). https://www.forestresearch.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/fthr/forestgales/how-forestgales-works/ [accessed 05/07/22] Quine, C.P., White, I.M.S. (1993) Revised Windiness Scores for the Windthrow Hazard Classification: the Revised Scoring Method. Information Note No. 230. Forestry Commission, Edinburgh.
E	Physical restrictions	Inland Water	OS Mastermap® Topographic Layer https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/mastermap-topography [accessed 05/07/22]
E	Physical restrictions	Roads, Railways	OS Mastermap® Topographic Layer https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/mastermap-topography [accessed 05/07/22]
E	Policy	Gardens, designed landscapes	Historic Environment Scotland (2021) Gardens, designed landscapes. https://data.gov.uk/dataset/bab10bd8-cc8b-4b4e-9eb7-d620a3ee27d9/gardens-and-designed-landscapes [accessed 05/07/22]
E	Policy	SSSI & SAC (not wood, not Salmon)	Scottish Government (2021) Special Area of Conservation (Scotland). https://data.gov.uk/dataset/2559b8bc-ddd6-4cb1-8a98-9422e1b1865a/special-area-of-conservation-scotland [accessed 05/07/22] Scottish Government (2021) Site of Special Scientific Interest (Scotland). https://data.gov.uk/dataset/d64bf689-4ce8-465b-b00e-6a57dec94a22/site-of-special-scientific-interest-scotland [accessed 05/07/22]
E	Policy	Scheduled Monuments	Historic Environment Scotland (2021) Scheduled Monuments. https://data.gov.uk/dataset/9075113f-d8e3-48da-bbfc-34f58939529b/scheduled-monuments [accessed 05/07/22]
E	Soil	Deep Peat & carbon rich soils (SNH)	Scottish Natural Heritage (SNH) (2016) Carbon and Peatland 2016 map. https://spatialdata.gov.scot/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/51b36efb-3521-4243-9bb0-93f8a7a60a71 [accessed 05/07/22]
E	Soil	Wet soils (not good for productive trees)	Boorman, D B, Hollis, J M & Lilly, A 1995. Hydrology of soil types: a hydrologically based classification of the soils of the United Kingdom. Institute of Hydrology Report No. 126. 137pp. https://www.ceh.ac.uk/data/hydrology-soil-types-1km-grid
E	Topography	Slope above 15 degree rise (100m, from 10m DTM hydrologically corrected)	Machala M., Baggio-Compagnucci A., Gimona, A. (2012) Hydrological correction of the OS DTM, part of InVEST Nitrogen Export Modelling Workflow. Internal report. Ordnance Survey (2009) Land-Form PROFILE® DTM, © Crown copyright and database rights 2020 Ordnance Survey (100025252). https://digimap.edina.ac.uk/help/files/resource-hub/downloads/osmanuals/land-form-profile-user-guide_5_4.pdf [accessed 26/11/24] Lovell, Sarah T.; Bentrup, Gary; Stanek, Erik. (2022). Agroforestry at the Landscape Level. In: Garrett, Harold E. "Gene"; Jose, Shibu; Gold, Michael A., eds. North American Agroforestry, 3rd Edition. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.: 417-435. Chapter 14. https://doi.org/10.1002/9780891183785.ch14

Appendix 4-2. All layers included in the Agroforestry zonation, cf. Appendix 4-1 for references. Colour coding is as follows, blue: target layers, purple: positive layers, orange: negative layers, black: exclusion layers.

Appendix 4-3. Main components and final landscape zonation (0 to 1) for Agroforestry (left). Calculation of the Final continuous map (right) = rescaled (Positive + Negative) x Exclusion x Target.

Appendix 4-4. Final 3 tiers zonation for Agroforestry, in the brackets: hectare and % of Scotland extent.

Appendix 5. Hedgerows and field margins in cropland systems (AEM)

There are several opportunities to increase environmental sustainability of cropland systems.

Hedgerows, which can also be considered as part of broadly agroforestry, are a prime example of an effective measure in arable landscapes. They are not only carbon sinks, with established hedge networks storing tens of tons of carbon per hectare but also play a vital role in enhancing biodiversity (including pollinators). Planting new hedges (and rejuvenating existing ones) are low-impact strategies for addressing climate change and boosting biodiversity in arable systems.

Field margins, when taken out of production, significantly benefit wildlife. They lead to increased populations of various wild species, including those crucial for ecosystem services like pollination and pest regulation. Additionally, soil carbon levels are higher under grass margins compared to under annual crops. These margins also help in preventing soil erosion and water pollution.

Field margins and hedgerows can also be part of an integrated pest management strategy. By reducing the reliance on pesticides, they decrease diffuse pollution.

We call these intervention agro-environmental measures (AEM) on the maps.

Appendix 5-1. Layers included in the AEM zonation maps. The “Type” column refers to Equation 1 with T: target areas, P: positive criteria, N: negative criteria, E: exclusion areas. Cf. Appendix 5-2 for individual maps.

Type	Topic	Name	Reference
T	Agriculture	Arable (LCM19)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O’Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc
T	Topography	Fields boundaries - binary	Wardell-Johnson, D. (2022) Stocking rates derived from IACS 2019 version 4. Based on data from Land Parcel Information System (2019) courtesy of Rural Payments and Inspections Division, Scottish Government. Based on data from the June Agricultural Census (2019) courtesy of Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services, Agricultural Statistics team, Scottish Government.
P	Connectivity corridors	Broadleaves connectivity corridors	Castellazzi M., Gimona A. (2018). Lemmings tool: assessing functional connectivity based on random walk of individuals in a vector landscape under land use and climate change - Part of RESAS 1.4.2cii [Deliverable 10] - Beta version of vector-based connectivity tool. Castellazzi, M.; Baggio, A.; Gimona, A., (2021) Climate-friendly (inspired by NetZero) land use scenario for multi-benefits: assessing broadleaves connectivity with the Lemmings tool., Part of RESAS O1.4.2ciiD29: Connectivity Analysis for Forests and Heather Habitats. (PowerPoint Summary). Gimona, A., Poggio, L., Brown, I., Castellazzi, M. (2012) Woodland networks in a changing climate: Threats from land use change. Biological Conservation. Vol 149, issue 1, p.93-102. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.01.060 Morton D., Rowland C., Wood C., Meek L., Marston c., Smith G., Wadsworth R., Simpson I.C. (2011) Final Report for LCM2007 - the new UK Land Cover Map. CEH. https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/LCM2007%20Final%20Report.pdf Patterson G., Nelson, D., Robertson P., Tullis J. (2014) Scotland’s Native Woodlands Results from the Native Woodland Survey of Scotland. Forestry Commission Scotland, Edinburgh, UK. Forestry Commission (2015) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2015. https://www.forestresearch.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/national-forest-inventory/ [accessed 05/07/22]
P	Fluvial risk	Fluvial risk (high; from EcoForest tool)	Gimona, A., Castellazzi, M., Wilkins B., Baggio-Compagnucci, A. (2022) ECOFOREST: Spatial multi-criteria analysis to prioritise planting at the landscape level, Metadata and Further information - Fluvial Risk. Online. https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/212a7f8600314ad38d074769c3500f61#ref-n-9zP92k [accessed 07/01/25]
P	Pollination	Pollination for food production (low)	Gimona, A., Baggio-Compagnucci, A., Poggio, L., Brooker R., Pakeman, R., Simonetti E., Castellazzi, M. (2018) Indicators of Ecosystem Services in Scotland, including Pollination Index. https://arcg.is/0v04WH [accessed 05/07/22]

P	Rivers	Nutrient export (high) on Arable (LCM19)	Sharp, R., Tallis, H.T., Ricketts, T., Guerry, A.D., Wood, S.A., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Nelson, E., Ennaanay, D., Wolny, S., Olwero, N. and Vigerstol, K., (2014). InVEST 3.0.0 User's Guide. The Natural Capital Project: Stanford University, University of Minnesota, The Nature Conservancy, and World Wildlife Fund. https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest
P	Rivers	Risk of Phosphorus leaching (high)	For non-agricultural land : implementation of rules of the PLUS+ model for slope and land cover. Donnelly, D., Booth, P., Ferrier, R., Futter, M. (2011) Phosphorus Land Use and Slope (PLUS+) Model, User Guide & Computer code (version 1.6). https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/Plus+%20User%20Guide%20-%20v1_6.pdf [accessed 09/01/25] For agricultural land : Gagkas, Z., Lilly, A., Baggaley, N., Stutter, M. (2019) Development of framework for a Red-Amber-Green assessment on phosphorus application to land. Technical report. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34519.19365
P	Rivers	Sediment export (high) on Arable (LCM19)	Sharp, R., Tallis, H.T., Ricketts, T., Guerry, A.D., Wood, S.A., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Nelson, E., Ennaanay, D., Wolny, S., Olwero, N. and Vigerstol, K., (2014). InVEST 3.0.0 User's Guide. The Natural Capital Project: Stanford University, University of Minnesota, The Nature Conservancy, and World Wildlife Fund. https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest
P	Rivers	Water Overall Ecology 2023, Bad and Poor catchments	SEPA (2024) Water Classification Hub: Overall Ecology for 2023, surface water. https://informatics.sepa.org.uk/WaterClassificationHub/ [accessed 05/12/24] "Contains SEPA data © Scottish Environment Protection Agency and database right [2023]. All rights reserved" Open Government Licence version 3.0 . Required Acknowledgements: © SEPA. Some features of this information are based on digital spatial data licensed from the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology © NERC (CEH). Contains OS data © Crown copyright [and database right].
P	Soil	Carbon Budget (Positive)	Baggio-Compagnucci A., Ovando P., Hewitt R.J., Canullo R., Gimona, A. (2022) Barking up the wrong tree? Can forest expansion help meet climate goals? Environmental Science & Policy. vol.136, p.237-249. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.05.011 .

Appendix 5-2. All layers included in the AEM zonation, cf. Appendix 5-1 Appendix 2-1 for references. Colour coding is as follows, blue: target layers, purple: positive layers, orange: negative layers, black: exclusion layers.

Appendix 5-3. Main components and final landscape zonation (0 to 1) for AEM systems (left). Calculation of the Final continuous map (right) = rescaled (Positive + Negative) x Exclusion x Target.

Appendix 5-4. Final 3 tiers zonation for AEM systems, in the brackets: hectare and % of Scotland extent.

Appendix 6. High Nature Value Grasslands (HNVG)

Appendix 6-a. HNVG – Decreased grazing pressure to promote floral diversity

Despite grasslands covering around one third Scotland, only about 2%, is made up of semi-natural grasslands rich in biodiversity and carbon (NatureScot, 2024). These grasslands can give an important contribution to both preserving biodiversity and preventing GHG emissions, especially if stocking rates on them are managed for conservation purposes.

Acid grasslands, mainly in upland areas, are particularly significant as they hold approximately 30% more soil carbon than other types. Similarly, neutral grasslands, which have a higher species richness compared to improved grasslands, also store more carbon in their topsoil. Enhancing species diversity in these grasslands is important for reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and supporting broader biodiversity.

The restoration of a portion of the present permanent (improved) intensively grazed by converting it to species-rich grassland would be beneficial for both biodiversity and GHG emission reduction (Farm Advisory Service, 2024). This restoration could be part of creating varied, multi-functional landscape mosaics, supporting a characteristic pool of species.

Significantly lowering stocking rates would improve biodiversity and save several Megatons of CO₂-equivalent methane emissions from animals per year. And the management of the spatial and temporal pattern of grazing intensity might lead to higher carbon sequestration improving fertility and water retention.

In some grasslands, integrating tree planting through agroforestry or wood pasture could also provide benefits such as shelter and shade, timber, and provision of habitat, but could also encroach on open-ground species such as waders.

Appendix 6-1. Layers included in the HNVG – Decreased grazing pressure to promote floral diversity zonation maps. The “Type” column refers to Equation 1 with T: target areas, P: positive criteria, N: negative criteria, E: exclusion areas. Cf. Appendix 6-2 for individual maps.

Type	Topic	Name	Reference
T	Grazing	All Grasslands (IG, SNG) - grazed above conservation threshold	Baseline dataset from : Castellazzi, M., Gimona, A., Wardell-Johnson, D., Miller, D., Rivington, M., & Matthews, K. (2024). A SSP1-Low emission land use scenario based on LCM2019 for Scotland - baseline 2019 and scenario 2050 (nov22) [Data set]. https://openscience.hutton.ac.uk/dataset/low-emission-land-use-scenarios , Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10927157 Based on the following : Wardell-Johnson, D. (2022) IACS 2019 v4. Based on data from Land Parcel Information System (2019) courtesy of Rural Payments and Inspections Division, Scottish Government. Based on data from the June Agricultural Census (2019) courtesy of Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services, Agricultural Statistics team, Scottish Government. Morton, R.D., Marston, C.G., O’Neil, A.W., Rowland, C.S., (2020) Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc SSP1-Low emission story map: https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/c3d3feff85f14460b6c973127089d6f9
P	Agriculture	Grasslands (improved & semi-natural; LCM19)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O’Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc

P	Conservation	Grass conservation + 2km	Pakeman, R., McKeen, M. (2019). Within country targeting of agri-environment funding: A test of different methods. <i>Global Ecology and Conservation</i> . 17. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00574 Gimona, A., McKeen, M., Baggio, A., Simonetti, E., Poggio, L., Pakeman, R.J. (2023) Complementary effects of biodiversity and ecosystem services on spatial targeting for agri-environment payments. <i>Land Use Policy</i> 126, 106532. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106532
P	Pollination	Pollination for food production (low)	Gimona, A., Baggio-Compagnucci, A., Poggio, L., Brooker R., Pakeman, R., Simonetti E., Castellazzi, M. (2018) Indicators of Ecosystem Services in Scotland, including Pollination Index. https://arcg.is/0v04WH [accessed 05/07/22]
P	Rivers	Water Overall Ecology 2023, Bad and Poor catchments	SEPA (2024) Water Classification Hub: Overall Ecology for 2023, surface water. https://informatics.sepa.org.uk/WaterClassificationHub/ [accessed 05/12/24] “Contains SEPA data © Scottish Environment Protection Agency and database right [2023]. All rights reserved” Open Government Licence version 3.0 . Required Acknowledgements: © SEPA. Some features of this information are based on digital spatial data licensed from the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology © NERC (CEH). Contains OS data © Crown copyright [and database right].

Appendix 6-2. All layers included in the HNMG – Decreased grazing pressure to promote floral diversity zonation, cf. Appendix 6-1 for references. Colour coding is as follows, blue: target layers, purple: positive layers, orange: negative layers, black: exclusion layers.

Appendix 6-3. Main components and final landscape zonation (0 to 1) for HNVG – Decreased grazing pressure to promote floral diversity (left). Calculation of the Final continuous map (right) = rescaled (Positive + Negative) x Exclusion x Target.

Appendix 6-4. Final 3 tiers zonation for HNVG – Decreased grazing pressure to promote floral diversity, in the brackets: hectare and % of Scotland extent.

Appendix 6-b. HNVG – Woodland removal for open ground birds

Ground nesting bird species, and especially waders, suffer from “predation shadow” from wooded habitat because predators such as foxes and corvids, which often inhabit and hunt from woodland edges, preying upon nests in adjacent open habitats. Thus woodlands within Grass conservation areas are targeted. Note that the status of protected or ancient woodlands is currently not taken in account in this analysis.

Appendix 6-5. Layers included in the High Nature Value Grasslands woodland removal for open ground birds zonation maps. The “Type” column refers to Equation 1 with T: target areas, P: positive criteria, N: negative criteria, E: exclusion areas. Cf. Appendix 6-6 for individual maps.

Type	Topic	Name	Reference
T	Conservation	Grass conservation + 2km	Pakeman, R., McKeen, M. (2019). Within country targeting of agri-environment funding: A test of different methods. <i>Global Ecology and Conservation</i> . 17. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00574 Gimona, A., McKeen, M., Baggio, A., Simonetti, E., Poggio, L., Pakeman, R.J. (2023) Complementary effects of biodiversity and ecosystem services on spatial targeting for agri-environment payments. <i>Land Use Policy</i> 126, 106532. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106532
T	Existing woodlands	Existing woodlands (LCM19 + FC 2020)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O’Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). https://open-data-Caledonian-Pinewood-Inventory-data.gov.uk Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2020, https://data-forestry.opendata.arcgis.com/datasets/0681a879417b42dfb6d7825ef791cd5a_0/explore?location=56.121863%2C-4.501302%2C6.98 Castellazzi, M., Udugbezi, E., Gimona, A., Hare, M. (2023) Milestone: D4-4, WP1, M1.1. Vulnerability of native woodlands under different climate scenarios. Internal report for milestone. March 2023

Appendix 6-6. All layers included in the High Nature Value Grasslands woodland removal for open ground birds zonation, cf. Appendix 6-5 for references. Colour coding is as follows, blue: target layers, purple: positive layers, orange: negative layers, black: exclusion layers.

Appendix 6-7. Main components and final landscape zonation (0 to 1) for High Nature Value Grasslands woodland removal for open ground birds (left). Calculation of the Final continuous map (right) = rescaled (Positive + Negative) x Exclusion x Target.

Appendix 6-8. Final 3 tiers zonation for High Nature Value Grasslands woodland removal for open ground birds, in the brackets: hectare and % of Scotland extent.

Appendix 7. Heathlands

Heathlands are habitats whose successional character is often frozen by management. They represent significant carbon stores, mainly in their soils.

Management preserves a pool of characteristic species, but sometimes it might conflict with other objectives. One of the key concerns is soil disturbance, which can lead to increased carbon emissions. Therefore, prioritizing soil conservation and minimizing disturbance is crucial for mitigating carbon release from these ecosystems. When heathlands experience encroachment by shrubs or trees, there's a risk of carbon release from the soil, which may not be compensated by the carbon absorbed by the new vegetation for many years. Therefore, woodland expansion on heathlands needs to be done carefully if carbon retention is a concern.

Moderate grazing on heathlands can improve habitat quality, but its impact on (animal) greenhouse gas emissions varies depending on the grazing species, stocking rate, and breeds. In upland areas, reducing grazing levels of both domestic and wild herbivores and more strategic targeting of suitable areas for burning can enhance carbon sequestration. Restoring overgrazed heathlands by significantly reducing grazing pressure would increase soil carbon stocks and avoid the loss of heathland specialist species and other open ground species, thus striking a balance between climate actions and biodiversity.

Appendix 7-1. Layers included in the Heathland zonation maps below. The "Type" column refers to Equation 1 with T: target areas (Ta: additive instead of a multiplication), P: positive criteria, N: negative criteria, E: exclusion areas. Cf. Appendix 7-2 for individual maps.

Type	Topic	Name	Reference
Ta	Grazing	Heathers & Heathers grasslands grazed above conservation threshold	Baseline dataset from : Castellazzi, M., Gimona, A., Wardell-Johnson, D., Miller, D., Rivington, M., & Matthews, K. (2024). A SSP1-Low emission land use scenario based on LCM2019 for Scotland - baseline 2019 and scenario 2050 (nov22) [Data set]. https://opendscience.hutton.ac.uk/dataset/low-emission-land-use-scenarios , Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10927157 Based on the following : Wardell-Johnson, D. (2022) IACS 2019 v4. Based on data from Land Parcel Information System (2019) courtesy of Rural Payments and Inspections Division, Scottish Government. Based on data from the June Agricultural Census (2019) courtesy of Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services, Agricultural Statistics team, Scottish Government. Morton, R.D., Marston, C.G., O'Neil, A.W., Rowland, C.S., (2020) Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc SSP1-Low emission story map: https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/c3d3feff85f14460b6c973127089d6f9
Ta	Grazing	Wild deer count (NatureScot, 2010) above 5 deer / km ²	NatureScot (2010) Deer Counts Deer groups. https://opendata.nature.scot/datasets/snh::deer-counts-deer-groups/about [accessed 11/12/24] © Scottish Natural Heritage; Available under the Open Government Licence http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/
P	Conservation	Grass conservation + 2km	Pakeman, R., McKeen, M. (2019). Within country targeting of agri-environment funding: A test of different methods. <i>Global Ecology and Conservation</i> . 17. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00574 Gimona, A., McKeen, M., Baggio, A., Simonetti, E., Poggio, L., Pakeman, R.J. (2023) Complementary effects of biodiversity and ecosystem services on spatial targeting for agri-environment payments. <i>Land Use Policy</i> 126, 106532. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106532
P	Conservation	Moorland high connectivity	Castellazzi M., Gimona A. (2018). Lemmings tool: assessing functional connectivity based on random walk of individuals in a vector landscape under land use and climate change - Part of RESAS 1.4.2cii [Deliverable 10] - Beta version of vector-based connectivity tool. Castellazzi M., Hewitt R., Gimona A. (2021) SSP1 & SSP5 land use scenarios (50 replicates, November 2020) to estimate 3 Habitats connectivity (Broadleaves, Moorland, Scot Pine) with the Lemmings tool [part of RESAS O1.4.2ciiD29: Connectivity analysis for forests and heather habitats]. Powerpoint Summary.

Ersoy, E., Jorgensen, A, Warren, P.H. (2019) Identifying multispecies connectivity corridors and the spatial pattern of the landscape. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*. Vol 40, pp.308-322 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2018.08.001>. [adapted for land use classes and model characteristics]

Morton D., Rowland C., Wood C., Meek L., Marston c., Smith G., Wadsworth R., Simpson I.C. (2011) Final Report for LCM2007 - the new UK Land Cover Map. CEH. <https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/LCM2007%20Final%20Report.pdf>

Patterson G., Nelson, D., Robertson P., Tullis J. (2014) Scotland's Native Woodlands Results from the Native Woodland Survey of Scotland. Forestry Commission Scotland, Edinburgh, UK.

Forestry Commission (2015) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2015. <https://www.forestresearch.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/national-forest-inventory/> [accessed 05/07/22]

Scottish Government (2015) Integrated Administrative and Control System (IACS) for 2015. <https://www.ruralpayments.org/topics/apply-for-funding/single-application-form/> [accessed 05/07/22]

Appendix 7-2. All layers included in the Heathlands zonation, cf. Appendix 7-1 for references. Colour coding is as follows, blue: target layers, purple: positive layers, orange: negative layers, black: exclusion layers.

Appendix 7-3. Main components and final landscape zonation (0 to 1) for Heathlands (left). Calculation of the Final continuous map (right) = rescaled (Positive + Negative) x Exclusion x Target.

Appendix 7-4. Final 3 tiers zonation for Heathland, in the brackets: hectare and % of Scotland extent.

Appendix 8. Freshwater ecosystems

Freshwater ecosystems harbour a characteristic pool of species and are increasingly vulnerable to climate change. While standing waters are also important, in this work we only addressed running waters, due to data availability and resource constraints.

Changes in rainfall patterns pose risks of both flooding and drought, while rising water temperatures threaten species that require cool waters.

Addressing these challenges requires a holistic approach encompassing whole catchments.

Tree planting along riversides can protect biodiversity by providing shade and cooling, and extending riparian forests into headwater streams can create thermal refuges and help moderate temperature fluctuations.

A catchment-wide approach can also alleviate flood risks and soil erosion (although it cannot stop flooding during very large rainfall events). This approach includes tree planting in strategic areas of the catchment, but also installing log structures, creating temporary storage ponds, removing flood embankments, and re-meandering rivers. Because tree planting has other co-benefits, it is often worth pursuing by carefully targeting planting areas, also minding trade-offs, e.g. with soil carbon storage.

Appendix 8-a. Riparian woodland – General

Riparian woodlands play an important role in supporting biodiversity in areas adjacent to rivers and streams. These woodlands act as natural buffers, protecting water quality, reducing erosion, and improving habitats for a variety of wild species. Recognizing their importance, the landscape zonation mapping includes riparian woodlands as a key component. This opportunity map builds on the Scottish Forestry’s zonation (2023), integrating 13 specific criteria from their riparian woodlands grant scheme. Most of the data on which the SF zonation is based were provided by the authors and created in the [RIVERTOOL project](#). The final zonation combines the SF’s zonation with data from wildlife dispersal corridors and Nature Scot’s riparian woodlands, highlighting opportunities for expanding this habitat in proportion to the criteria met.

Appendix 8-1. Layers included in the Riparian woodland - general zonation maps. The “Type” column refers to Equation 1 with T: target areas, P: positive criteria, N: negative criteria, E: exclusion areas. Cf. Appendix 8-2 for individual maps.

Type	Topic	Name	Reference
T	Riparian	FGS Target Woodlands for Riparian Benefits (Scottish Forestry, JHI-Rivertool)	Scottish Forestry (2023) FGS Target Area - Woodlands for Riparian Benefits. https://spatialdata.gov.scot/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/0c7fa87e-00cc-4f69-9fca-ea8c00fda240 Gimona A., Castellazzi, M. Wilkins B., Baggio-Compagnucci A. (2023) Rivertool - (Riparian Vegetation Ecosystem Services-based Ranking Tool) Methods, Tutorial, Data. https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/f49964c9d7344ac4a6056cbde3122946
P	Connectivity corridors	100m ring from woodlands (LCM19, FC2020)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O’Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). https://open-data-Caledonian-Pinewood-Inventory-data.gov.uk Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2020, https://data-forestry.opendata.arcgis.com/datasets

			/0681a879417b42dfb6d7825ef791cd5a_0/ explore?location=56.121863%2C-4.501302%2C6.98 Castellazzi, M., Udugbezi, E., Gimona, A. , Hare, M. (2023) Milestone: D4-4, WP1, M1.1. Vulnerability of native woodlands under different climate scenarios. Internal report for milestone. March 2023
P	Connectivity corridors	Riparian Woodland (NatureScot) + 100m Buffer	NatureScot (2023) Riparian Woodland Scotland. https://spatialdata.gov.scot/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/ac10398e-a9ec-427f-bd9f-116582e95c0d
P	Rivers	Water Overall Ecology 2023, Bad and Poor catchments	SEPA (2024) Water Classification Hub: Overall Ecology for 2023, surface water. https://informatics.sepa.org.uk/WaterClassificationHub/ [accessed 05/12/24] "Contains SEPA data © Scottish Environment Protection Agency and database right [2023]. All rights reserved." Open Government Licence version 3.0. Required Acknowledgements: © SEPA. Some features of this information are based on digital spatial data licensed from the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology © NERC (CEH). Contains OS data © Crown copyright [and database right].
E	Existing woodlands	Existing woodlands (LCM19)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc
E	Existing woodlands	Woodlands FC (2020)	Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). https://open-data-Caledonian-Pinewood-Inventory-data.gov.uk Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2020, https://data-forestry.opendata.arcgis.com/datasets/0681a879417b42dfb6d7825ef791cd5a_0/ explore?location=56.121863%2C-4.501302%2C6.98 Castellazzi, M., Udugbezi, E., Gimona, A. , Hare, M. (2023) Milestone: D4-4, WP1, M1.1. Vulnerability of native woodlands under different climate scenarios. Internal report for milestone. March 2023

Appendix 8-2. All layers included in the Riparian woodland – general zonation, cf. Appendix 8-1 for references. Colour coding is as follows, blue: target layers, purple: positive layers, orange: negative layers, black: exclusion layers.

Appendix 8-3. Main components and final landscape zonation (0 to 1) for Riparian woodland – general (left). Calculation of the Final continuous map (right) = rescaled (Positive + Negative) x Exclusion x Target.

Appendix 8-4. Final 3 tiers zonation for Riparian woodlands - general, in the brackets: hectare and % of Scotland extent.

Appendix 8-b. Riparian woodland – Thermal stress (includes salmon)

Appendix 8-5. Layers included in the Riparian woodland – thermal stress zonation maps. The “Type” column refers to Equation 1 with T: target areas, P: positive criteria, N: negative criteria, E: exclusion areas. Cf. Appendix 8-6 for individual maps.

Type	Topic	Name	Reference
T	Rivers	River Shading (incl. salmon)	Jackson, F. L., Fryer, R. J., Hannah, D. M., Millar, C.P., and Malcolm, I. A. (2018) A spatio-temporal statistical model of maximum daily river temperatures to inform the management of Scotland's Atlantic salmon rivers under climate change. <i>Science of The Total Environment.</i> , 612, 1543-1558. Jackson, F.L., Hannah, D.M., Ouellet, V. and Malcolm, I.A. (2021) A deterministic river temperature model to prioritise the management of riparian woodland to mitigate high river temperatures under climate change. <i>Hydrological Processes.</i>
P	Connectivity corridors	100m ring from woodlands (LCM19, FC2020)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). https://open-data-Caledonian Pinewood Inventory - data.gov.uk Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2020, https://data-forestry.opendata.arcgis.com/datasets/0681a879417b42dfb6d7825ef791cd5a_0/explore?location=56.121863%2C-4.501302%2C6.98 Castellazzi, M., Udugbezi, E., Gimona, A., Hare, M. (2023) Milestone: D4-4, WP1, M1.1. Vulnerability of native woodlands under different climate scenarios. Internal report for milestone. March 2023
P	Connectivity corridors	Riparian Woodland (NatureScot) + 100m Buffer	NatureScot (2023) Riparian Woodland Scotland. https://spatialdata.gov.scot/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/ac10398e-a9ec-427f-bd9f-116582e95c0d
P	Riparian	Riparian Vegetation Improvement (high; from EcoForest tool)	Gimona, A., Castellazzi, M., Wilkins B., Baggio-Compagnucci, A. (2022) ECOFOREST: Spatial multi-criteria analysis to prioritise planting at the landscape level, Metadata and Further information - Riparian Vegetation Improvement. Online. https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/212a7f8600314ad38d074769c3500f61#ref-n-bmlmQt [accessed 07/01/25] Scottish Environment Protection Agency (2016) Riparian Vegetation Planting Opportunities (25m) - Dataset. https://www.sepa.org.uk/environment/environmental-data/ [accessed 07/01/25]
E	Existing woodlands	Existing woodlands (LCM19)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc
E	Existing woodlands	Woodlands FC (2020)	Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). https://open-data-Caledonian Pinewood Inventory - data.gov.uk Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2020, https://data-forestry.opendata.arcgis.com/datasets/0681a879417b42dfb6d7825ef791cd5a_0/explore?location=56.121863%2C-4.501302%2C6.98 Castellazzi, M., Udugbezi, E., Gimona, A., Hare, M. (2023) Milestone: D4-4, WP1, M1.1. Vulnerability of native woodlands under different climate scenarios. Internal report for milestone. March 2023

Appendix 8-6. All layers included in the Riparian woodland – thermal stress (includes salmon), cf. Appendix 8-5 for references. Colour coding is as follows, blue: target layers, purple: positive layers, orange: negative layers, black: exclusion layers.

Appendix 8-7. Main components and final landscape zonation (0 to 1) for Riparian woodland – thermal stress (left). Calculation of the Final continuous map (right) = rescaled (Positive + Negative) x Exclusion x Target.

Appendix 8-8. Final 3 tiers zonation for Riparian woodlands – thermal stress, in the brackets: hectare and % of Scotland extent.

Appendix 9. Full metadata of GIS input layers

Appendix 9-1. List of abbreviations for the metadata table below (Appendix 9-2).

Abbreviations in column headings (habitats)	Full name
Wood	Woodlands
DeerG	Decreasing deer pressure to support woodland regeneration
Agro	Agroforestry
AEM	Hedgerows and field margins in cropland systems (AEM)
HNVG-F	High Nature Value Grasslands (HNVG) – Decreased grazing for flora
HNVG-B	High Nature Value Grasslands (HNVG) – Woodland removal for birds
Heathl	Heathlands
RipG	Riparian woodland – General
RipT	Riparian woodland – Thermal stress (includes salmon)

Abbreviations within the table (types of layers; cf. equation 1)	Full name
T	Target layer (Multiplicative)
Ta	Target layer (Additive)
P	Positive layer
N	Negative layer
E	Exclusion layer

Appendix 9-2. Full metadata of all GIS layers used as inputs, with their topic, name, references/origin and in which habitat they are used and in what capacity (target layer, positive/negative layer or exclusion layer); cf. Appendix 9-1 for the abbreviations.

Topic	Name	Reference	Wood	Dee	Agro	AEM	HNVG	HNVG	Hea	Rip	RipT
			d	rG			G-F	G-B	thl	G	
Agriculture	Arable (LCM19)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc				T					
Agriculture	Arable + Grasslands (improved & semi-natural; LCM19)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc			T						
Agriculture	Grasslands (improved & semi-natural; LCM19)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc					P				
Connectivity corridors	100m ring from woodlands (LCM19, FC2020)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). https://open-data-Caledonian-Pinewood-Inventory-data.gov.uk Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2020, https://data-forestry.opendata.arcgis.com/datasets/0681a879417b42dfb6d7825ef791cd5a_0/explore?location=56.121863%2C-4.501302%2C6.98 Castellazzi, M., Udugbezi, E., Gimona, A., Hare, M. (2023) Milestone: D4-4, WP1, M1.1. Vulnerability of native woodlands under different climate scenarios. Internal report for milestone. March 2023							P	P	
Connectivity corridors	Broadleaves connectivity corridors	Castellazzi M., Gimona A. (2018). Lemmings tool: assessing functional connectivity based on random walk of individuals in a vector landscape under land use and climate change - Part of RESAS 1.4.2cii [Deliverable 10] - Beta version of vector-based connectivity tool.	P		P	P					

Topic	Name	Reference	Wood	Deer	Agro	AEM	HNV G-F	HNV G-B	Heath	Rip G	RipT
		Castellazzi, M.; Baggio, A.; Gimona, A., (2021) Climate-friendly (inspired by NetZero) land use scenario for multi-benefits: assessing broadleaves connectivity with the Lemmings tool., Part of RESAS O1.4.2ciiD29: Connectivity Analysis for Forests and Heather Habitats. (PowerPoint Summary). Gimona, A., Poggio, L., Brown, I., Castellazzi, M. (2012) Woodland networks in a changing climate: Threats from land use change. Biological Conservation. Vol 149, issue 1, p.93-102. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.01.060									
		Morton D., Rowland C., Wood C., Meek L., Marston c., Smith G., Wadsworth R., Simpson I.C. (2011) Final Report for LCM2007 – the new UK Land Cover Map. CEH. https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/LCM2007%20Final%20Report.pdf Patterson G., Nelson, D., Robertson P., Tullis J. (2014) Scotland's Native Woodlands Results from the Native Woodland Survey of Scotland. Forestry Commission Scotland, Edinburgh, UK. Forestry Commission (2015) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2015. https://www.forestryresearch.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/national-forest-inventory/ [accessed 05/07/22]									
Connectivity corridors	Riparian Woodland (NatureScot) + 100m Buffer	NatureScot (2023) Riparian Woodland Scotland. https://spatialdata.gov.scot/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/ac10398e-a9ec-427f-bd9f-116582e95c0d								P	P
Connectivity corridors	ScotPines connectivity corridors	Castellazzi M., Gimona A. (2018). Lemmings tool: assessing functional connectivity based on random walk of individuals in a vector landscape under land use and climate change - Part of RESAS 1.4.2cii [Deliverable 10] - Beta version of vector-based connectivity tool. Castellazzi, M.; Baggio, A.; Gimona, A., (2021) Climate-friendly (inspired by NetZero) land use scenario for multi-benefits: assessing broadleaves connectivity with the Lemmings tool., Part of RESAS O1.4.2ciiD29: Connectivity Analysis for Forests and Heather Habitats. (PowerPoint Summary). Scottish Forestry Open Data (2018) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). Caledonian Pinewood Inventory - data.gov.uk [accessed 05/07/22] NatureScot (2019) National Vegetation Classification (NVC) survey. SpatialData.gov.scot [accessed 05/07/22] Patterson G., Nelson, D., Robertson P., Tullis J. (2014) Scotland's Native Woodlands Results from the Native Woodland Survey of Scotland. Forestry Commission Scotland, Edinburgh, UK. https://forestry.gov.scot/publications/74-scotland-s-native-woodlands-results-from-the-native-woodland-survey-of-scotland/download [accessed 05/07/22] Forestry Commission (2015) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2015. National Forest Inventory - Forest Research [accessed 05/07/22] Morton D., Rowland C., Wood C., Meek L., Marston c., Smith G., Wadsworth R., Simpson I.C. (2011) Final Report for LCM2007 – the new UK Land Cover Map. CEH. https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/LCM2007%20Final%20Report.pdf	P		P						
Conservation	Arable conservation + 2km on	Pakeman, R., McKeen, M. (2019). Within country targeting of agri-environment funding: A test of different methods. Global Ecology and Conservation. 17. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00574 Gimona, A., McKeen, M., Baggio, A., Simonetti, E., Poggio, L., Pakeman, R.J. (2023) Complementary effects of biodiversity and ecosystem services on spatial targeting for agri-environment payments. Land Use Policy 126, 106532. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106532	E			E					
Conservation	Grass conservation + 2km on	Pakeman, R., McKeen, M. (2019). Within country targeting of agri-environment funding: A test of different methods. Global Ecology and Conservation. 17. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00574 Gimona, A., McKeen, M., Baggio, A., Simonetti, E., Poggio, L., Pakeman, R.J. (2023) Complementary effects of biodiversity and ecosystem services on spatial targeting for agri-environment payments. Land Use Policy 126, 106532. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106532	E		E		P	T	P		
Conservation	Moorland high connectivity on	Castellazzi M., Gimona A. (2018). Lemmings tool: assessing functional connectivity based on random walk of individuals in a vector landscape under land use and climate change - Part of RESAS 1.4.2cii [Deliverable 10] - Beta version of vector-based connectivity tool. Castellazzi M., Hewitt R., Gimona A. (2021) SSP1 & SSP5 land use scenarios (50 replicates, November 2020) to estimate 3 Habitats connectivity (Broadleaves, Moorland, Scot Pine) with the Lemmings tool [part of RESAS O1.4.2ciiD29: Connectivity analysis for forests and heather habitats]. Powerpoint Summary. Ersoy, E., Jorgensen, A, Warren, P.H. (2019) Identifying multispecies connectivity corridors and the spatial pattern of the landscape. Urban Forestry & Urban Greening. Vol 40, pp.308-322 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2018.08.001 . [adapted for land use classes and model characteristics] Morton D., Rowland C., Wood C., Meek L., Marston c., Smith G., Wadsworth R., Simpson I.C. (2011) Final Report for LCM2007 – the new UK Land Cover Map. CEH. https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/LCM2007%20Final%20Report.pdf Patterson G., Nelson, D., Robertson P., Tullis J. (2014) Scotland's Native Woodlands Results from the Native Woodland Survey of Scotland. Forestry Commission Scotland, Edinburgh, UK. Forestry Commission (2015) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2015. https://www.forestryresearch.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/national-forest-inventory/ [accessed 05/07/22] Scottish Government (2015) Integrated Administrative and Control System (IACS) for 2015. https://www.ruralpayments.org/topics/apply-for-funding/single-application-form/ [accessed 05/07/22]	E		E					P	
Conservation	Natural regeneration (1km from native woodlands)	Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). https://open-data-Caledonian-Pinewood-Inventory-data.gov.uk Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2020, https://data-forestry.opendata.arcgis.com/datasets/0681a879417b42dfb6d7825ef791cd5a_0/explore?location=56.121863%2C-4.501302%2C6.98				P					
Conservation	Top Waders outside conservation (0.5Mha) + 2km on	Newey, S., Fielding, D., Wilson, M. (2020) Mapping farmland wader distributions and population change to identify wader priority areas for conservation and management action. https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/Newey_etal_IdentifyingWaderPriorityAreas_InternallyReviewed%26%20Signedoff_FINAL.pdf [accessed 05/07/22] Conservation areas: available from https://data.gov.uk/	E			E					
Conservation	Waders in riparian habitat within protected areas	Newey, S., Fielding, D., Wilson, M. (2020) Mapping farmland wader distributions and population change to identify wader priority areas for conservation and management action. https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/Newey_etal_IdentifyingWaderPriorityAreas_InternallyReviewed%26%20Signedoff_FINAL.pdf [accessed 05/07/22] OS Mastermap® Networks Water Layer https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/mastermap-water [accessed 05/07/22] Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information	E			E					

Topic	Name	Reference	Woo d	Dee rG	Agro	AEM	HNV G-F	HNV G-B	Hea thl	Rip G	RipT
Conservation	Waders outside Conservation areas	Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc Protected areas: available from https://data.gov.uk/ Newey, S., Fielding, D., Wilson, M. (2020) Mapping farmland wader distributions and population change to identify wader priority areas for conservation and management action. https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/Newey_eta_IdentifyingWaderPriorityAreas_InternallyReviewed%26%20Signedoff_FINAL.pdf [accessed 05/07/22] Conservation areas: available from https://data.gov.uk/	N		N						
Existing woodlands	Existing woodlands (LCM19 + FC 2020)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). https://open-data-Caledonian-Pinewood-Inventory-data.gov.uk Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2020, https://data-forestry.opendata.arcgis.com/datasets/0681a879417b42dfb6d7825ef791cd5a_0/explore?location=56.121863%2C-4.501302%2C6.98 Castellazzi, M., Udugbezi, E., Gimona, A., Hare, M. (2023) Milestone: D4-4, WP1, M1.1. Vulnerability of native woodlands under different climate scenarios. Internal report for milestone. March 2023						T			
Existing woodlands	Existing woodlands (LCM19)	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc								E	E
Existing woodlands	Woodlands FC (2020)	Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). https://open-data-Caledonian-Pinewood-Inventory-data.gov.uk Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) National Forest Inventory Woodland Scotland 2020, https://data-forestry.opendata.arcgis.com/datasets/0681a879417b42dfb6d7825ef791cd5a_0/explore?location=56.121863%2C-4.501302%2C6.98 Castellazzi, M., Udugbezi, E., Gimona, A., Hare, M. (2023) Milestone: D4-4, WP1, M1.1. Vulnerability of native woodlands under different climate scenarios. Internal report for milestone. March 2023								E	E
Fluvial risk	Fluvial risk (high; from EcoForest tool)	Gimona, A., Castellazzi, M., Wilkins B., Baggio-Compagnucci, A. (2022) ECOFOREST: Spatial multi-criteria analysis to prioritise planting at the landscape level, Metadata and Further information - Fluvial Risk. Online. https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/212a7f8600314ad38d074769c3500f61#ref-n-9zP92k [accessed 07/01/25]	P		P	P					
Grasslands	All grasslands + heathers	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc	T								
Grazing	All Grasslands (A, IG, SNG) - grazed above conservation threshold	Baseline dataset from : Castellazzi, M., Gimona, A., Wardell-Johnson, D., Miller, D., Rivington, M., & Matthews, K. (2024). A SSP1-Low emission land use scenario based on LCM2019 for Scotland - baseline 2019 and scenario 2050 (nov22) [Data set]. https://openscience.hutton.ac.uk/dataset/low-emission-land-use-scenarios , Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10927157 Based on the following : Wardell-Johnson, D. (2022) IACS 2019 v4. Based on data from Land Parcel Information System (2019) courtesy of Rural Payments and Inspections Division, Scottish Government. Based on data from the June Agricultural Census (2019) courtesy of Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services, Agricultural Statistics team, Scottish Government. Morton, R.D., Marston, C.G., O'Neil, A.W., Rowland, C.S., (2020) Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc SSP1-Low emission story map: https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/c3d3feff85f14460b6c973127089d6f9									P
Grazing	All Grasslands (IG, SNG) - grazed above conservation threshold	Baseline dataset from : Castellazzi, M., Gimona, A., Wardell-Johnson, D., Miller, D., Rivington, M., & Matthews, K. (2024). A SSP1-Low emission land use scenario based on LCM2019 for Scotland - baseline 2019 and scenario 2050 (nov22) [Data set]. https://openscience.hutton.ac.uk/dataset/low-emission-land-use-scenarios , Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10927157 Based on the following : Wardell-Johnson, D. (2022) IACS 2019 v4. Based on data from Land Parcel Information System (2019) courtesy of Rural Payments and Inspections Division, Scottish Government. Based on data from the June Agricultural Census (2019) courtesy of Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services, Agricultural Statistics team, Scottish Government. Morton, R.D., Marston, C.G., O'Neil, A.W., Rowland, C.S., (2020) Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc SSP1-Low emission story map: https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/c3d3feff85f14460b6c973127089d6f9						T			
Grazing	All land grazed above conservation threshold	Baseline dataset from : Castellazzi, M., Gimona, A., Wardell-Johnson, D., Miller, D., Rivington, M., & Matthews, K. (2024). A SSP1-Low emission land use scenario based on LCM2019 for Scotland - baseline 2019 and scenario 2050 (nov22) [Data set]. https://openscience.hutton.ac.uk/dataset/low-emission-land-use-scenarios , Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10927157 Based on the following : Wardell-Johnson, D. (2022) IACS 2019 v4. Based on data from Land Parcel Information System (2019) courtesy of Rural Payments and Inspections Division, Scottish Government. Based on data from the June Agricultural Census (2019) courtesy of Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services, Agricultural Statistics team, Scottish Government. Morton, R.D., Marston, C.G., O'Neil, A.W., Rowland, C.S., (2020) Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc SSP1-Low emission story map: https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/c3d3feff85f14460b6c973127089d6f9									P

Topic	Name	Reference	Wood	Deer	Agro	AEM	HNV G-F	HNV G-B	Health	Rip G	RipT
Grazing	Heathers & Heathers grasslands grazed above conservation threshold	Baseline dataset from : Castellazzi, M., Gimona, A., Wardell-Johnson, D., Miller, D., Rivington, M., & Matthews, K. (2024). A SSP1-Low emission land use scenario based on LCM2019 for Scotland - baseline 2019 and scenario 2050 (nov22) [Data set]. https://openscience.hutton.ac.uk/dataset/low-emission-land-use-scenarios , Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10927157 Based on the following : Wardell-Johnson, D. (2022) IACS 2019 v4. Based on data from Land Parcel Information System (2019) courtesy of Rural Payments and Inspections Division, Scottish Government. Based on data from the June Agricultural Census (2019) courtesy of Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services, Agricultural Statistics team, Scottish Government. Morton, R.D., Marston, C.G., O'Neil, A.W., Rowland, C.S., (2020) Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc SSP1-Low emission story map: https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/c3d3feff85f14460b6c973127089d6f9								Ta	
Grazing	Wild deer count (NatureScot, 2010) above 5 deer / km2	NatureScot (2010) Deer Counts Deer groups. https://opendata.nature.scot/datasets/snh:deer-counts-deer-groups/about [accessed 11/12/24] © Scottish Natural Heritage; Available under the Open Government Licence http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/		T						Ta	
Physical restrictions	(sub-)Urban, rocks, sediments, water from LCM19	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc	E		E						
Physical restrictions	Bog, Fen from LCM19	Morton, R. D.; Marston, C. G.; O'Neil, A. W.; Rowland, C. S. (2020). Land Cover Map 2019 (25m rasterised land parcels, GB). NERC Environmental Information Data Centre. (Dataset). https://doi.org/10.5285/f15289da-6424-4a5e-bd92-48c4d9c830cc	E		E						
Physical restrictions	DAMs score (High winds)	Forest Research (2015) Detailed Aspect Method of Scoring (DAMS). https://www.forestresearch.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/fthr/forestgales/how-forestgales-works/ [accessed 05/07/22] Quine, C.P., White, I.M.S. (1993) Revised Windiness Scores for the Windthrow Hazard Classification: the Revised Scoring Method. Information Note No. 230. Forestry Commission, Edinburgh.	E		E						
Physical restrictions	Inland Water	OS Mastermap® Topographic Layer https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/mastermap-topography [accessed 05/07/22]	E		E						
Physical restrictions	Roads, Railways	OS Mastermap® Topographic Layer https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/mastermap-topography [accessed 05/07/22]	E		E						
Policy	Gardens, designed landscapes	Historic Environment Scotland (2021) Gardens, designed landscapes. https://data.gov.uk/dataset/bab10bd8-cc8b-4b4e-9eb7-d620a3ee27d9/gardens-and-designed-landscapes [accessed 05/07/22]	E		E						
Policy	SSSI & SAC (not wood, not Salmon)	Scottish Government (2021) Special Area of Conservation (Scotland). https://data.gov.uk/dataset/2559b8bc-ddd6-4cb1-8a98-9422e1b1865a/special-area-of-conservation-scotland [accessed 05/07/22] Scottish Government (2021) Site of Special Scientific Interest (Scotland). https://data.gov.uk/dataset/d64bf689-4ce8-465b-b00e-6a57dec94a22/site-of-special-scientific-interest-scotland [accessed 05/07/22]	E		E						
Policy	Scheduled Monuments	Historic Environment Scotland (2021) Scheduled Monuments. https://data.gov.uk/dataset/9075113f-d8e3-48da-bbfc-34f58939529b/scheduled-monuments [accessed 05/07/22]	E		E						
Pollination	Pollination for food production (low)	Gimona, A., Baggio-Compagnucci, A., Poggio, L., Brooker R., Pakeman, R., Simonetti E., Castellazzi, M. (2018) Indicators of Ecosystem Services in Scotland, including Pollination Index. https://arxiv.org/abs/1804.04444 [accessed 05/07/22]	P		P	P	P				
Regeneration woodlands	1km buffer around Native Broadleaves (NWSS)	Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about			P						
Regeneration woodlands	1km buffer around Native Coniferous (CPI, NWSS)	Forestry Commission Scotland, (2020) Caledonian Pinewood Inventory (CPI). https://open-data-Caledonian-Pinewood-Inventory-data.gov.uk Scottish Forestry, (2021) Native Woodland Survey of Scotland (NWSS), https://open-data-scottishforestry.hub.arcgis.com/datasets/6d27b064fcb471da50c8772ad0162d7_0/about			P						
Riparian	FGS Target Woodlands for Riparian Benefits (Scottish Forestry, JHI-Rivertool)	Scottish Forestry (2023) FGS Target Area - Woodlands for Riparian Benefits. https://spatialdata.gov.scot/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/0c7fa87e-00cc-4f69-9fca-ea8c00fda240 Gimona A., Castellazzi, M., Wilkins B., Baggio-Compagnucci A. (2023) Rivertool - (Riparian Vegetation Ecosystem Services-based Ranking Tool) Methods, Tutorial, Data. https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/f49964c9d7344ac4a6056cbde3122946								T	
Riparian	Riparian Vegetation Improvement (high; from EcoForest tool)	Gimona, A., Castellazzi, M., Wilkins B., Baggio-Compagnucci, A. (2022) ECOFOREST: Spatial multi-criteria analysis to prioritise planting at the landscape level, Metadata and Further information - Riparian Vegetation Improvement. Online. https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/212a7f8600314ad38d074769c3500f61#ref-n-bmImQt [accessed 07/01/25] Scottish Environment Protection Agency (2016) Riparian Vegetation Planting Opportunities (25m) - Dataset. https://www.sepa.org.uk/environment/environmental-data/ [accessed 07/01/25]									P
Rivers	Nutrient export (high)	Sharp, R., Tallis, H.T., Ricketts, T., Guerry, A.D., Wood, S.A., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Nelson, E., Ennaanay, D., Wolny, S., Olwero, N. and Vigerstol, K., (2014). InVEST 3.0.0 User's Guide. The Natural Capital Project: Stanford University, University of Minnesota, The Nature Conservancy, and World Wildlife Fund. https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest	P		P						
Rivers	Nutrient export (high) on Arable (LCM19)	Sharp, R., Tallis, H.T., Ricketts, T., Guerry, A.D., Wood, S.A., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Nelson, E., Ennaanay, D., Wolny, S., Olwero, N. and Vigerstol, K., (2014). InVEST 3.0.0 User's Guide. The Natural Capital Project: Stanford University, University of Minnesota, The Nature Conservancy, and World Wildlife Fund. https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest						P			
Rivers	Risk of Phosphorus leaching (high)	For non-agricultural land : implementation of rules of the PLUS+ model for slope and land cover. Donnelly, D., Booth, P., Ferrier, R., Futter, M. (2011) Phosphorus Land Use and Slope (PLUS+) Model, User Guide & Computer code (version 1.6). https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/Plus+%20User%20Guide%20-%20v1.6.pdf [accessed 09/01/25]	P		P	P					

Topic	Name	Reference	Wood	Deer	Agro	AEM	HNV G-F	HNV G-B	Health	Rip G	RipT
		For agricultural land : Gagkas, Z., Lilly, A., Baggaley, N., Stutter, M. (2019) Development of framework for a Red-Amber-Green assessment on phosphorus application to land. Technical report. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34519.19365									
Rivers	River Shading (incl. salmon)	Jackson, F. L., Fryer, R. J., Hannah, D. M., Millar, C. P., and Malcolin, I. A. (2018) A spatio-temporal statistical model of maximum daily river temperatures to inform the management of Scotland's Atlantic salmon rivers under climate change. <i>Science of The Total Environment.</i> , 612, 1543-1558. Jackson, F.L., Hannah, D.M., Ouellet, V. and Malcolin, I.A. (2021) A deterministic river temperature model to prioritise the management of riparian woodland to mitigate high river temperatures under climate change. <i>Hydrological Processes.</i>									T
Rivers	Sediment export (high)	Sharp, R., Tallis, H.T., Ricketts, T., Guerry, A.D., Wood, S.A., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Nelson, E., Ennaanay, D., Wolny, S., Olwero, N. and Vigerstol, K., (2014). InVEST 3.0.0 User's Guide. The Natural Capital Project: Stanford University, University of Minnesota, The Nature Conservancy, and World Wildlife Fund. https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest	P		P						
Rivers	Sediment export (high) on Arable (LCM19)	Sharp, R., Tallis, H.T., Ricketts, T., Guerry, A.D., Wood, S.A., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Nelson, E., Ennaanay, D., Wolny, S., Olwero, N. and Vigerstol, K., (2014). InVEST 3.0.0 User's Guide. The Natural Capital Project: Stanford University, University of Minnesota, The Nature Conservancy, and World Wildlife Fund. https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest					P				
Rivers	Water Overall Ecology 2023, Bad and Poor catchments	SEPA (2024) Water Classification Hub: Overall Ecology for 2023, surface water. https://informatics.sepa.org.uk/WaterClassificationHub/ [accessed 05/12/24] "Contains SEPA data © Scottish Environment Protection Agency and database right [2023]. All rights reserved". Open Government Licence version 3.0 . Required Acknowledgements: © SEPA. Some features of this information are based on digital spatial data licensed from the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology © NERC (CEH). Contains OS data © Crown copyright [and database right].	P		P	P	P			P	
Soil	Carbon Budget (Negative)	Baggio-Compagnucci A., Ovando P., Hewitt R.J., Canullo R., Gimona, A. (2022) Barking up the wrong tree? Can forest expansion help meet climate goals? <i>Environmental Science & Policy.</i> vol.136, p.237-249. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.05.011 .	N		N						
Soil	Carbon Budget (Positive)	Baggio-Compagnucci A., Ovando P., Hewitt R.J., Canullo R., Gimona, A. (2022) Barking up the wrong tree? Can forest expansion help meet climate goals? <i>Environmental Science & Policy.</i> vol.136, p.237-249. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.05.011 .	P			P					
Soil	Deep Peat & carbon rich soils (SNH)	Scottish Natural Heritage (SNH) (2016) Carbon and Peatland 2016 map. https://spatialdata.gov.scot/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/51b36efb-3521-4243-9bb0-93f8a7a60a71 [accessed 05/07/22]	E		E						
Soil	Wet soils (not good for productive trees)	Boorman, D B, Hollis, J M & Lilly, A 1995. Hydrology of soil types: a hydrologically based classification of the soils of the United Kingdom. Institute of Hydrology Report No. 126. 137pp. https://www.ceh.ac.uk/data/hydrology-soil-types-1km-grid						E			
Topography	Fields boundaries - binary	Wardell-Johnson, D. (2022) Stocking rates derived from IACS 2019 version 4. Based on data from Land Parcel Information System (2019) courtesy of Rural Payments and Inspections Division, Scottish Government. Based on data from the June Agricultural Census (2019) courtesy of Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services, Agricultural Statistics team, Scottish Government.							T		
Topography	Slope above 15 degree rise (100m, from 10m DTM hydrologically corrected)	Machala M., Baggio-Compagnucci A., Gimona, A. (2012) Hydrological correction of the OS DTM, part of InVEST Nitrogen Export Modelling Workflow. Internal report. Ordnance Survey (2009) Land-Form PROFILE® DTM, © Crown copyright and database rights 2020 Ordnance Survey (100025252). https://digimap.edina.ac.uk/help/files/resource-hub/downloads/osmanuals/land-form-profile-user-guide_5_4.pdf [accessed 26/11/24] Lovell, Sarah T.; Bentrup, Gary; Stanek, Erik. (2022). Agroforestry at the Landscape Level. In: Garrett, Harold E. "Gene"; Jose, Shibu; Gold, Michael A., eds. North American Agroforestry, 3rd Edition. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.: 417-435. Chapter 14. https://doi.org/10.1002/9780891183785.ch14								E	